

The Historical Evolution of Artificial Intelligence in Radiation Oncology: A PubMed-Based Bibliometric and Text-Mining Analysis

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Abstract

Purpose: To characterize the historical evolution and thematic structure of research on artificial intelligence (AI) in radiotherapy using a PubMed-based bibliometric and term co-occurrence analysis.

Materials and Methods: PubMed was searched on June 29, 2026, using a strategy combining MeSH and title/abstract terms for AI and radiotherapy. From 10,627 retrieved records, 7,106 human-study records were included. Terms were extracted from titles and abstracts in VOSviewer version 1.6.20 (0), using binary counting, a minimum occurrence threshold of 50, association-strength normalization, and a custom thesaurus for semantic harmonization.

Results: Among 100,640 identified terms, 652 met the occurrence threshold and the 60% most relevant terms were selected. After thesaurus-based normalization and exclusion of non-discriminatory expressions, the final network comprised 271 terms, 31,692 weighted links, and four thematic clusters. The largest and temporally earliest cluster addressed treatment planning, dosimetry, delivery, and technical workflow. The remaining clusters captured clinical prediction and radiomics, deep learning and medical imaging, and automated delineation with geometric performance assessment. Recent terms included large language model, interpretability, decision curve analysis, diagnostic accuracy, and transformer architectures.

Conclusions: The AI-in-radiotherapy literature has evolved from technical automation and dosimetric optimization toward image-based deep learning, clinical prediction, and more recent concerns about interpretability, validation, and clinical utility. The field remains highly interconnected, linking technical workflows with personalized outcome modelling and image-guided automation.

Keywords: artificial intelligence; radiation oncology; radiotherapy; bibliometrics; VOSviewer; text mining; machine learning; deep learning.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has progressively transformed radiation oncology from a predominantly technology-driven discipline into a data-intensive clinical specialty. Early computational applications were mainly focused on rule-based automation, image processing, and treatment-planning optimization. More recently, the field has expanded to encompass machine learning, deep learning, radiomics, automated segmentation, dose prediction, adaptive radiotherapy, treatment quality assurance, toxicity modelling, outcome prediction, and generative AI.

Radiotherapy is particularly suited to AI development because its clinical workflow integrates multimodal imaging, anatomical delineations, dose distributions, treatment-delivery data, and longitudinal outcomes. Contemporary reviews consistently identify image segmentation, treatment planning, and quality assurance

as central application domains, while clinical translation increasingly depends on robust validation, workflow integration, and end-user trust [2-4].

Although the volume of publications has expanded rapidly, it remains difficult to describe the field's historical structure, to distinguish mature from emerging themes, and to determine how technical and clinical strands of research are connected. Bibliometric text mining provides a useful framework to study these questions by identifying recurrent terms, quantifying their co-occurrence patterns, and assigning them to thematic clusters [1].

The aim of this study was to characterize the historical evolution of research on AI in radiotherapy using publications indexed in PubMed. Specifically, we sought to identify the major thematic domains of the field, quantify their interrelationships, and examine temporal changes through term co-occurrence mapping using VOSviewer.

Materials and Methods

Study design and data source

A bibliometric and text-mining analysis was conducted using records retrieved from PubMed, the biomedical literature database maintained by the U.S. National Library of Medicine. PubMed was selected because of its broad coverage of peer-reviewed biomedical and clinical literature and its integration of Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) with title and abstract indexing.

The search was performed on June 29, 2026. No publication-date restriction was applied. Records were retrieved using a strategy designed to identify publications at the intersection of AI and radiotherapy, combining controlled vocabulary and free-text terms in titles and abstracts. The strategy was designed to improve sensitivity for recent publications that may not yet have been fully indexed with MeSH terms.

Search strategy

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(
  "Artificial Intelligence"[Mesh]
  OR "Machine Learning"[Mesh]
  OR "Deep Learning"[Mesh]
  OR "Neural Networks, Computer"[Mesh]
  OR "artificial intelligence"[Title/Abstract]
  OR "machine learning"[Title/Abstract]
  OR "deep learning"[Title/Abstract]
  OR "neural network*" [Title/Abstract]
  OR "computer vision"[Title/Abstract]
  OR "natural language processing"[Title/Abstract]
  OR "large language model*" [Title/Abstract]
  OR LLM[Title/Abstract]
  OR "generative AI"[Title/Abstract]
)
AND
(
  "Radiotherapy"[Mesh]
  OR "Radiotherapy Planning, Computer-Assisted"[Mesh]
  OR "Radiotherapy Dosage"[Mesh]
  OR radiotherap* [Title/Abstract]
  OR "radiation therap*" [Title/Abstract]
  OR "radiation oncology"[Title/Abstract]
  OR "radiation treatment" [Title/Abstract]
  OR "radiation treatment planning" [Title/Abstract]
  OR "treatment planning" [Title/Abstract]
  OR IMRT[Title/Abstract]
  OR VMAT[Title/Abstract]
)
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OR SBRT[Title/Abstract]
OR SABR[Title/Abstract]
OR brachytherap*[Title/Abstract]
)

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The initial search retrieved 10,627 records. The PubMed human-studies filter was then applied, yielding a final corpus of 7,106 records for bibliometric analysis.

Data preparation and term co-occurrence analysis

Bibliographic records were exported from PubMed in a VOSviewer-compatible format, including titles, abstracts, publication years, authors, journal information, and indexing metadata where available. Title and abstract fields were selected for term extraction because this approach has greater thematic sensitivity than title-only analysis and permits identification of technical and clinical concepts that may not appear in titles.

Term co-occurrence analysis was performed using VOSviewer version 1.6.20 (0) [1]. Terms were extracted automatically from titles and abstracts. Binary counting was selected, so each term contributed once per publication regardless of the number of mentions. A minimum occurrence threshold of 50 publications per term was applied. The co-occurrence network was normalized using association strength, and clusters were generated using the VOSviewer clustering algorithm.

A dedicated thesaurus file was developed before final network generation to harmonize spelling variants, abbreviations, singular/plural forms, and conceptually equivalent expressions. Examples included standardization of CBCT and cone-beam CT as cone-beam computed tomography; OAR/OARs as organ at risk; IMRT as intensity-modulated radiotherapy; VMAT as volumetric modulated arc therapy; SBRT/SABR as stereotactic body radiotherapy; auto/automatic segmentation as automated segmentation; and Dice/DSC variants as dice similarity coefficient. Generic or non-discriminatory expressions, including bibliographic, temporal, and broad methodological terms, were excluded where they did not improve thematic discrimination.

The final network was visualized in network, overlay, and density modes. For the overlay visualization, the average publication year of documents containing each term was used to distinguish established from emerging topics. Clusters were interpreted using their representative terms, occurrence frequencies, total link strength (TLS), and temporal position.

Analytic workflow

Step	Result
Initial PubMed retrieval	10,627 records
Human-study filter applied	7,106 records
Automatically identified title/abstract terms	100,640
Terms meeting the minimum occurrence threshold (>=50 publications)	652
Most relevant terms retained by VOSviewer relevance score	391 (60%)
Final terms after thesaurus normalization and exclusions	271
Weighted co-occurrence links	31,692
Total link strength	430,590
Final clusters	4

Table 1. Search and analytic workflow.

Results

Network structure and cluster-level characteristics

After semantic normalization and exclusion of non-discriminatory terms, the final co-occurrence network comprised 271 terms connected by 31,692 weighted links, with a total link strength of 430,590. The network was distributed across four clusters of unequal size and thematic specificity (Table 2). The presence of substantial inter-cluster links indicates that AI research in radiotherapy has developed as an interconnected field rather than as a collection of isolated subdisciplines.

Cluster	Terms	Occurrences	TLS	Weighted mean year	Provisional thematic label
1	112	24,226	341,817	2021.39	Planning, dosimetry, delivery, and technical workflow
2	84	19,284	266,340	2022.65	Clinical prediction, radiomics, prognosis, and model evaluation
3	57	14,779	190,487	2022.90	Deep learning, medical imaging, and emerging AI architectures
4	18	4,264	62,536	2022.49	Automated delineation and geometric performance assessment

Table 2. Quantitative characteristics of the four term co-occurrence clusters. TLS, total link strength.

Thematic interpretation of the clusters

Cluster 1: AI for radiotherapy planning, dosimetry, treatment delivery, and technical workflow optimization. Cluster 1 was the largest and temporally earliest cluster (112 terms; occurrence-weighted mean publication year, 2021.39). It was anchored by terms related to dose, dose distribution, organ at risk, adaptive radiotherapy, optimization, cone-beam computed tomography, and quality assurance. This cluster represents the technical foundation of AI in radiation oncology, encompassing treatment planning, dose calculation and prediction, delivery, adaptive workflows, and the evaluation of normal-tissue and target-dose metrics.

Cluster 2: Clinical prediction, radiomics, prognosis, and personalized outcome modelling. Cluster 2 contained 84 terms and was characterized by prediction, area under the receiver operating characteristic curve, machine learning model, predictive model, clinical outcome, radiomics, prognosis, toxicity, and survival. It represents the clinical and prognostic translation of AI, integrating clinical, imaging, radiomic, and treatment-related features for risk stratification, response modelling, and outcome prediction.

Cluster 3: Deep learning, medical imaging, computer vision, and emerging AI architectures. Cluster 3 contained 57 terms and had the most recent occurrence-weighted mean publication year among the major clusters (2022.90). Its structure was dominated by segmentation, diagnosis, convolutional neural network, classification, detection, magnetic resonance imaging, transformer, attention mechanism, and large language model. This cluster captures the expansion of deep-learning and computer-vision methods from image segmentation toward image interpretation, diagnostic applications, and more recent neural architectures.

Cluster 4: Automated delineation, segmentation validation, and geometric performance assessment. Cluster 4 was the smallest but most semantically focused group (18 terms). It was centered on dice similarity coefficient, delineation, Hausdorff distance, automated segmentation, manual delineation, clinical target volume, and gross tumor volume. The separation of this cluster from the wider imaging cluster indicates that automated contouring has matured into a distinct research domain, where geometric metrics, expert comparison, and clinical acceptability have become central topics.

Thematic interpretation of the AI-radiotherapy clusters

A bibliometric map from technical automation toward clinical prediction, imaging intelligence, and validated implementation

Figure 1. Schematic interpretation of the four thematic clusters identified in the AI-radiotherapy co-occurrence network.

Cluster	Representative term	Occurrences	TLS	Avg. pub. year
1	Dose	959	13,066	2020.70
1	Organ at risk	446	7,496	2022.49
1	Adaptive radiotherapy	397	5,520	2022.69
1	Cone-beam computed tomography	260	3,830	2022.75
1	Quality assurance	147	1,901	2022.22
2	Prediction	1,238	16,485	2022.72
2	Machine learning model	438	6,040	2023.67
2	Radiomics	266	4,014	2023.62
2	Prognosis	265	3,564	2023.14
2	Interpretability	145	2,162	2024.99
3	Segmentation	1,068	13,883	2022.68
3	Convolutional neural network	696	9,420	2022.45
3	Diagnosis	742	8,580	2023.18
3	Transformer	171	2,311	2024.89
3	Large language model	82	790	2025.41
4	Dice similarity coefficient	811	11,715	2023.05
4	Delineation	586	8,638	2022.48

Cluster	Representative term	Occurrences	TLS	Avg. pub. year
4	Hausdorff distance	322	4,844	2023.02
4	Automated segmentation	273	4,112	2022.30
4	Manual delineation	225	3,424	2022.22

Table 3. Representative terms selected for their thematic specificity and occurrence frequency. Terms with broad methodological meaning were not selected for this summary table even when highly connected.

Inter-cluster connectivity

The strongest between-cluster relationships were observed between the technical radiotherapy workflow cluster and the clinical prediction cluster (TLS, 62,303), followed by the technical workflow and deep-learning imaging clusters (TLS, 61,316), and the clinical prediction and deep-learning imaging clusters (TLS, 52,550). These values support a model of progressive integration: technical optimization is closely linked to image-based automation and to outcome modelling, while imaging methods provide common inputs to both planning and clinical prediction.

Clusters	Relationship	Inter-cluster TLS
1 - 2	Technical workflow <-> Clinical prediction	62,303
1 - 3	Technical workflow <-> Deep learning and imaging	61,316
2 - 3	Clinical prediction <-> Deep learning and imaging	52,550
1 - 4	Technical workflow <-> Automated delineation	26,462
3 - 4	Deep learning and imaging <-> Automated delineation	15,115
2 - 4	Clinical prediction <-> Automated delineation	10,521

Table 4. Inter-cluster connectivity based on summed pairwise link strength.

Temporal evolution of thematic domains

Overlay visualization revealed a clear temporal progression. Earlier terms were concentrated in the planning and dosimetry cluster, including dose, dose distribution, intensity-modulated radiotherapy, volumetric modulated arc therapy, treatment delivery, and dosimetry. Terms related to automated segmentation, convolutional neural networks, computed tomography, cone-beam computed tomography, and delineation occupied an intermediate temporal position. More recent concepts included large language model (average publication year, 2025.41), interpretability (2024.99), transformer (2024.89), decision curve analysis (2024.68), diagnostic accuracy (2024.69), F1 score (2024.67), attention mechanism (2024.36), clinical utility (2024.27), and heterogeneity (2024.13).

Overall, the temporal overlay supports a historical shift from AI-driven technical automation and dosimetric optimization toward deep-learning-based image analysis, clinical prediction, and increasingly explicit attention to explainability, validation, and clinical utility.

Discussion

Principal findings

This PubMed-based analysis describes a coherent historical trajectory in AI research in radiotherapy. The field was initially dominated by technical workflows, including planning, dosimetry, delivery, organs-at-risk management, and quality assurance. It subsequently expanded through computer-vision applications, with deep learning and image segmentation becoming major research areas. More recently, the thematic center of gravity has shifted toward clinical prediction, radiomics, interpretability, and model evaluation. The four-cluster structure therefore captures not merely a topical classification, but a progression from automation of individual technical tasks to more integrated data-driven clinical support.

Technical automation remains the historical foundation

The earliest and largest cluster was related to planning, dosimetry, treatment delivery, and quality assurance. This finding is consistent with the intrinsically data-rich and protocolized nature of radiotherapy, where AI can leverage structured imaging, contours, dose distributions, and delivery information. Recent reviews continue to identify segmentation, treatment planning, and quality assurance as the core operational applications of AI in radiotherapy [2,3]. The strong linkage between the technical cluster and both image-based and predictive clusters in the present network suggests that these early applications did not become obsolete; rather, they provide the infrastructure and data foundation for later advances.

From image analysis to clinically evaluated auto-contouring

The separation of automated delineation and geometric performance assessment into a distinct cluster is notable. It suggests that auto-contouring is no longer represented only by model-development terminology but has developed its own evaluation culture, centered on Dice similarity coefficient, Hausdorff distance, expert comparison, and target-volume definitions. This is aligned with contemporary evidence that AI-based segmentation in radiotherapy must be evaluated not only on geometric similarity but also on clinical usability and the need for expert review, especially for targets and anatomically challenging structures [5]. The dedicated contouring cluster may therefore represent the transition from algorithmic feasibility to workflow-sensitive validation.

Clinical prediction and radiomics as the main translational axis

The clinical prediction cluster linked radiomics, survival, toxicity, prognosis, response, and risk stratification with performance-assessment terms such as area under the receiver operating characteristic curve and cross-validation. This configuration reflects the translational ambition of AI in radiation oncology: moving beyond automation to estimate patient-specific outcomes and support treatment individualization. However, the network also highlights the centrality of validation and evaluation terms, indicating that predictive performance alone is increasingly insufficient. The emergence of clinical utility and decision curve analysis suggests a recent effort to assess whether models can improve decisions rather than merely discriminate outcomes.

Emerging themes: architecture, interpretability, and implementation

The most recent terms included transformer, attention mechanism, large language model, interpretability, diagnostic accuracy, and clinical utility. The average publication year of the large language model term (2025.41) should be interpreted as an indicator of very recent thematic emergence rather than evidence of established clinical deployment. In parallel, the prominence of interpretability and clinical utility reflects growing recognition that high-performing models require transparency, reliability, and integration into real

clinical workflows. These requirements are particularly important in radiation oncology, where clinical implementation must account for data-model dependency, uncertainty, safety, and end-user oversight [4,7-9].

Interconnected rather than siloed development

The strongest links occurred between technical workflow and clinical prediction, and between technical workflow and deep-learning imaging. This pattern indicates that research in AI and radiotherapy is structured around shared data and workflow dependencies. Image acquisition and segmentation inform planning; planning and dose data inform toxicity and outcome modelling; and clinical outcomes provide the endpoints necessary to evaluate technical interventions. This interdependence supports multidisciplinary development and evaluation strategies that involve radiation oncologists, medical physicists, dosimetrists, imaging specialists, data scientists, and patients.

Methodological strengths and limitations

Strengths of this study include the broad PubMed retrieval strategy, the inclusion of both MeSH and free-text terms, title-and-abstract term extraction, use of binary counting, and semantic normalization through a dedicated thesaurus. The analysis also combines structural and temporal information through network and overlay visualizations. The main limitations should also be recognized. First, only PubMed was used as the bibliographic source, which may underrepresent conference proceedings, biomedical engineering literature, and non-indexed publications. Second, term co-occurrence reflects the language used in publications, not necessarily methodological quality, clinical validity, or real-world adoption. Third, thesaurus construction and inclusion thresholds incorporate partly subjective decisions, despite being applied before final network generation. Fourth, average publication year is a descriptive temporal indicator and does not demonstrate causality or effective technological adoption.

Implications

The historical structure identified here can help frame future research priorities. Technical AI tools should be evaluated not only for computational performance but also for clinical benefit, workflow impact, and safety. Predictive models should move beyond internal discrimination metrics toward external validation, calibration, clinical utility, and prospective evaluation. For emerging generative and language-model applications, the priority should be rigorous governance, transparent human oversight, and clearly defined roles within clinical workflows. These themes are increasingly central to safe and effective clinical implementation of AI in radiation oncology [4,7,8].

Conclusions

The literature on AI in radiotherapy has evolved from a technical focus on treatment planning, dosimetry, delivery, and quality assurance toward deep-learning-based imaging, automated delineation, clinical prediction, radiomics, and decision-support applications. The four-cluster network demonstrates that these domains are closely interconnected. Recent thematic signals emphasize advanced neural architectures, interpretability, clinical utility, and large language models, suggesting that the next phase of the field will be defined not only by algorithmic innovation but also by robust validation, safety, and meaningful clinical integration.

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Use of artificial intelligence as support

AI-based tools were used as editorial support during preparation of this manuscript, including language refinement, structural consistency checks, and review of clarity. The authors retained full responsibility for the study design, PubMed search, data processing, analysis, interpretation, reference verification, and final manuscript content. No AI tool was used as an autonomous source of scientific evidence or as a substitute for human expert judgment.

Abbreviations and acronyms

AI: Artificial intelligence.

CBCT: Cone-beam computed tomography.

CT: Computed tomography.

DL: Deep learning.

DSC: Dice similarity coefficient.

IMRT: Intensity-modulated radiotherapy.

LLM: Large language model.

MeSH: Medical Subject Headings.

ML: Machine learning.

OAR: Organ at risk.

SABR: Stereotactic ablative radiotherapy.

SBRT: Stereotactic body radiotherapy.

TLS: Total link strength.

VMAT: Volumetric modulated arc therapy.